

PROGNOSTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF CARDIAC MARKERS IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH GASTROINTESTINAL BLEEDING

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ABSTRACT

The use of new oral anticoagulants as efficient antithrombotic medications is common in clinical settings. Examples include the direct thrombin inhibitor dabigatran and the selective (XA) factor inhibitors rivaroxaban and apixaban. These medications have the ability to cause G-B without the need for oral administration. The case histories of 150 patients with gastrointestinal bleeding were retrospectively analyzed, and it was shown that 66.67% of the patients were men and 33.33% were women. Heart disease affected 22% of the patients, and the cardiac output fraction was -38.32.11%. After being admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU), 24 hours after admission, and 48 hours after admission, dynamic changes in cardiac biomarkers were examined. The BNP concentration was 30 times higher than the upper limit of normal at the first stage and decreased in dynamics ($p_1 < 0.001$) at later stages. CK-MB was high at stage I and 1.25 times at stage II ($p_1 < 0.05$); in stage III, it decreased by 1.76 times ($p_1 < 0.01$). The concentration of cTn was 27.66 times higher than normal in stage I. 1.64 times in stage II ($p_1 < 0.05$); in stage III, it decreased by 2.45 times ($p_1 < 0.01$). Based on the results of cardiac markers, these markers are of great prognostic value in the treatment of gastrointestinal bleeding. In the course of the studies, it was found that, despite heart damage, in 33 out of 150 patients, the concentration of troponin was high in 43.33% of patients, and the BNP concentration was high in 40% of patients. We do not consider it appropriate to use hemostatic drugs in these patients. During treatment, high doses of proton pump inhibitors, fresh frozen plasma, drugs that improve cardiac metabolism, and intravenous nitroglycerin are recommended.

Keywords: ischemic heart diseases, myocardial infarction, gastrointestinal bleeding, proton pump inhibitors, troponin, brain natriuretic peptide, cardiac biomarkers.

INTRODUCTION

Since 2009, using straight oral anticoagulants has been associated with significant gastrointestinal bleeding [1]. Increased usage of antiplatelet medications (APD) in cardiovascular diseases, notably in geriatric and senile patients, results in greater gastrointestinal bleeding (GIB) [2]. The risk of significant bleeding increases with the length of APD treatment [3].

PURPOSE

We discuss our findings in our research on the predictive significance of cardiac indicators in the management of G-B patients. Based on patient histories and laboratory test numbers, the Ethics Committee granted the co-authors permission to write articles while keeping the patients' identity. We are aware of the Republic of Azerbaijan's Ministry of Health's resolution No. 137

from December 29, 2011 regarding the standards for physicians' ethical behavior.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In 2015-2022 we analyzed the clinical materials of 150 patients who applied with a diagnosis of "Gastrointestinal bleeding". 100 patients (66.67%) are men, 50 patients (33.33%) are women. Patients aged 20-40 years - 20 (13.33%) people; 12 (8%) patients aged 41-50 years; 46 (30.67%) patients aged 51-60 years; Patients with 60+ are 72 (48%) people. The age of the patients was 56.44 ± 21.03 years, weight 73.81 ± 7.56 kg. Patients who applied to the hospital underwent appropriate examinations. The diagnosis was established on the basis of generally accepted clinical and anamnestic, laboratory, functional examinations (FEGDS, ECG, EchoCG), general and biochemical blood tests, respira-

tion, metabolism and cardiopanel, brain natriuretic peptide (BNP), an extensive coagulogram, the acid-base balance of the blood was also studied. Duodenal ulcer in 50% of patients; gastric ulcer in 14.67%; 5.33% had esophageal varices; 13.33% had a malignant gastric ulcer; 6.67% had anastomotic ulcer after resection of the stomach according to Bilroth II; Mallory-Weiss syndrome in 4%; In 3.33% of cases, necrotic lesions of the mucous membranes after a chemical burn of the esophagus, and in 2.67% of cases of rupture of the lower 1/3 of the esophagus caused gastrointestinal bleeding. 48 out of 150 patients (32%) regularly take antiplatelet agents (warfarin, rivaroxaban, clopidogrel, etc.); 6 people (4%) were taking steroid and non-steroid drugs orally due to a history of rheumatoid arthritis and bronchial asthma. 64% of patients did not take any medications and received specialized treatment in a hospital with a diagnosis of GIB. In addition, 80.67% of the 150 patients had comorbidities. Only 33 (22%) of these patients had heart disease and a history of oral antiplatelet agents, and the cardiac output fraction in the EXO study was $-38.3 \pm 2.11\%$. In 3.22% of patients, hypokinesia was noted on the posterior wall of the myocardium, in 1.29% - areas of akinesia. Profound anemia and home-

ostasis disorders developed in 58.71% of patients. 3 patients (2%) ended in death. Thus, the cause of death in 1 patient was respiratory failure as a result of myasthenia gravis, and in 2 patients acute heart failure developed as a result of acute coronary syndrome and cardiogenic shock. Statistical processing of the obtained numerical data: using the U-Wilcoxon (Mann-Whitney) rank test of quantitative indicators in the EXCEL-2010 spreadsheet, the average values and statistical errors of the obtained parameters were calculated, and the results were summarized in tables and charts.

RESULTS AND ITS DISCUSSION

Dynamic changes in cardiac biomarkers in patients were studied in 3 stages. Stage I, period included in ICU; Stage II - 24 hours after admission to the ICU; the third stage covers the next 48 hours. Cardiac biomarkers and enzymes in the blood can increase for various reasons: stress, inflammation, hypoxia during perfusion [8]. Myoglobin is considered a potential marker of cardiac muscle damage and assessment of cardiac function [10]. Since the specificity of elevated myoglobin is low, and creatine kinase (CK-MB), cardiac troponin (cTn), the study of brain natriuretic peptide (BNP) in the early prognosis of heart failure is of great diagnostic value, which is reflected in Table 1.

Table 1.

Dynamics of cardiac biomarkers

Indicators	Stage I	Stage II	Stage III
Brain natriuretic peptide (pg/ml)	15207,4 $\pm$ 1363,71	10395,41 $\pm$ 1003,88**	4521,7 $\pm$ 491,7***
Creatine kinase MB (U/l)	28,12 $\pm$ 3,82	22,41 $\pm$ 2,80*	16,01 $\pm$ 2,02**
Troponin ng/ml (cTn)	13,83 $\pm$ 2,07	8,45 $\pm$ 0,92*	5,65 $\pm$ 0,54*

Note: The statistical integrity of the difference between indicators at different stages in patients: Compared to stage I * - $p_1 < 0,05$; ** - $p_1 < 0,01$; *** - $p_1 < 0,01$.

The concentration of BNP was 30 times higher than the upper limit of normal at stage I and amounted to 15207.4 ± 1363.71 pg/ml. Although this indicator decreased by 1.46 times ($p_1 < 0.01$) in stage II, it remained

20.8 times higher than the upper limit of normal. At stage III, this indicator decreased by 3.36 times ($p_1 < 0.001$) compared with stage I, but remained 9.04 times higher than the upper limit of normal (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Dynamic changes of BNP in patients with GIB

Note: Statistics of the difference between indicators at different stages in patients integrity: compared to stage I * - $p_1 < 0,05$; ** - $p_1 < 0,01$; *** - $p_1 < 0,01$.

CK-MB in stage I was 28.12 ± 3.82 U/l, which exceeded the upper limit of the norm by 1.41 times. At the II stage, this indicator is 1.25 times higher than the I stage ($p_1 < 0.05$); At the III stage, it decreased by 1.76 times ($p_1 < 0.01$) compared to the I stage and reached the

normal level. The concentration of cTn in stage I was 13.83 ± 2.07 ng/ml, which is 27.66 times higher than normal. Although this indicator decreased by 1.64 times ($p_1 < 0.05$) in the II stage, it remained higher than the norm by 16.9 times. At the III stage, this indicator

decreased by 2.45 times ($p_1 < 0.01$) compared to the I stage, but remained higher than the norm by 11.3 times (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Dynamic changes of troponin (cTn) in patients with GIB

Note: Statistics of the difference between indicators at different stages in patients integrity: compared to stage I *- $p_1 < 0,05$; **- $p_1 < 0,01$; ***- $p_1 < 0,01$.

TREATMENT

Patients should undergo an urgent FEGDS examination during the treatment of acute GIB. In the treatment of patients who develop upper GIB, our first strategy is to reduce the erythrocyte mass to 5 ml/kg if $Hb < 9$ dc/l; With $PLT < 60 \times 10^3/l$, the platelet mass is 6.8 ml/kg; fresh frozen plasma 8 ml/kg, as well as colloidal solutions were transfused into iv. Additionally, proton pump inhibitors - 22 mcg / kg; aprotinin -30000 IU; drugs that improve the metabolism of the heart (Flazifin, Faziton, Sterlozin) 67.7 mg/kg per day; intravenous administration of potassium and antiarrhythmic drugs. Oxygen insufflation with a nasal cannula should also be applied regularly. In the case of Forest 1b, 6.68% used endoscopic electrocoagulation, 5.33% had ligatures for bleeding varicose veins. Given the presence of comorbidities identified using Forest 2c, patients were treated conservatively and recovered. Forest 1a identified 8% of patients on an emergency basis; 21.33% of patients identified with Forest 2a underwent elective surgery.

RESULT

In the course of our study, it was revealed that, despite heart failure, troponin concentration in 33 out of 150 patients in 65 (43.33%) patients; BNP concentration was high in 60 (40%) patients. Based on the results of cardiac markers, it can be said that these markers have a large prognostic value in the treatment of GIB. We do not consider it expedient to use hemostatic drugs in these patients. Because patients with GIB with high cardiac markers may develop myocardial infarction and heart failure.

DISCUSSION

According to Gridnev A.E. and co-authors, the use of hemostatic drugs (octreotide, etamsylate, aminocaproic acid, vikasol), etc., protein solutions, rheopolyglucin, prednisolone in the treatment of GIB is advisable. According to scientists, these drugs inhibit kinins, stabilize fibrin and its accumulation in the vascular beds, and cause aggregation of platelets and erythrocytes [6]. A number of scientists believe that aminocaproic acid and tranexan cannot prevent

coagulopathy in gastric bleeding caused by antiplatelet drugs [9,10]. Rao V.L. et al argue that bleeding should be controlled primarily endoscopically in patients with or without anticoagulant therapy [12]. Rhanderson N Cardoso believes that proton pump inhibitors should also be given long-term to patients with heart disease taking oral clopitogrel [13]. According to Truman J. Milling, it is reasonable to use the anticoagulant monoclonal antibody idarucizumab, produced by Boehringer Ingelheim under the brand name Praxbind, for patients with severe gastrointestinal bleeding receiving oral rivaroxaban from anticoagulants [14]. In an experiment, Wei Zhou et al. administered prothrombin complex concentrate (100 U/kg), mouse fresh frozen plasma (200 μ l) or recombinant human factor VIIa (1 mg/kg) during cerebral hemorrhage in mice treated with rivaroxaban. Prothrombin complex concentrate, factor VIIa, and fresh frozen plasma prevented the development of intracerebral hematoma associated with rivaroxaban [15]. Dhakal P. considers it more appropriate to use new generation drugs - prothrombin complex concentrate (Kofakt) with blood coagulation factors II, VII, IX and X in life-threatening gastric bleeding caused by the use of oral anticoagulants [4]. If GIB occurs in patients with chronic ischemic heart disease and atrial fibrillation receiving anticoagulant therapy, the European Heart Rhythm Association recommends stopping bleeding by conservative and endoscopic methods and reducing the dose of APD by promptly identifying a threat to the life of the patient. [5,7]. Pan K.L. and his co-authors consider it more appropriate to prescribe vitamin K preparation (Konaktion) as an antagonist along with the endoscopic method [11].

Thus, in the treatment of GIB by timely determination of the rate, volume, localization and type of bleeding of the source of blood loss, discontinuation of oral anticoagulants of direct action, as well as normalization of circulating blood volume with the use of proton pump inhibitors, aprotinin 30,000 Wh/day and fresh frozen plasma in large quantities we recommend dose infusion.

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